

Innovative Pedagogies and AI Integration in Nigerian Secondary Schools: Towards 21st-Century Learning

Chinelo Blessing Oribhabor

Department of Guidance and Counselling,

Faculty of Arts and Education,

University of Africa, Toru-Orua, Bayelsa State.

E-mail: chiblessing42004@yahoo.co.uk; chinelo.oribhabor@uat.edu.ng

OrcID: 0000-0002-7318-1477

Phone Number: 08034982069

This study investigates the integration of innovative pedagogies and Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Nigerian secondary schools to enhance teaching and learning outcomes, addressing the need for modern educational approaches amidst rapid digital advancements. Utilizing a quantitative research design, data were collected from 330 teachers and 30 administrators in Lagos, Edo, and Kaduna states through a validated survey instrument, resulting in a Cronbach's alpha of 0.86. Analysis revealed that while AI adoption in Nigerian secondary schools is limited, it holds significant potential for increasing classroom engagement, facilitating personalized teaching, and improving assessment methods. Key challenges identified include inadequate digital infrastructure, limited teacher training, curriculum misalignments, and socio-economic barriers. Schools adopting AI-driven practices early reported positive impacts on student engagement and teaching effectiveness. The research underscores the need for intentional improvements in infrastructure, curriculum updates, and equitable access to harness AI's potential in reshaping Nigerian secondary education. Practical recommendations for policy and practice are provided to support educational innovation.

Keywords:
Innovative,
Pedagogies, AI
Integration,
Secondary Schools,
21st-Century

Introduction

The 21st century has brought profound transformations in education, driven by advances in digital technology and the growing demand for skills such as critical thinking, collaboration, and digital literacy. Central to this shift is the integration of creative teaching methods and Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies, which are reshaping global educational practices. In advanced contexts, AI is increasingly applied

to support personalized learning, real-time assessment, intelligent tutoring, and administrative efficiency (Luckin et al., 2016; Holmes et al., 2019). In Nigeria, however, adoption remains uneven, limited by infrastructural gaps, weak policy support, and pedagogical constraints.

Nigeria's secondary education system plays a vital role in preparing learners for higher

education, employment, and civic participation. Yet it faces persistent challenges, including overcrowded classrooms, underqualified teachers, outdated curricula, and restricted access to technology (Adebayo & Olanrewaju, 2022). These constraints contribute to low student engagement and poor academic outcomes (UNESCO, 2021). While AI offers opportunities to bridge such gaps through adaptive learning platforms, automated grading tools, and data-driven dashboards, its implementation in Nigerian schools is still emerging.

Innovative pedagogies such as flipped classrooms, blended learning, inquiry-based learning, gamification, and project-based learning emphasize active, student-centered participation. When combined with AI, these methods can enhance differentiated instruction by analyzing learner data and tailoring content to individual needs (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). Localized educational solutions such as uLesson, Afrilearn, and pilot ChatGPT-based tutoring initiatives have already shown promising results in improving student outcomes (Adetutu-Awoyele et al., 2024; World Bank, 2023).

Empirical studies further reveal both optimism and skepticism. In Rivers State, teachers reported confidence in AI's potential to transform pedagogy (Chukwuma & Okeke, 2025), while school leaders in Edo State expressed awareness but emphasized the need for skill development, ethical frameworks, and infrastructure (Obanō & Osagie, 2025). Broader surveys reflect similar patterns: enthusiasm about AI's usefulness for lesson planning and concept simplification (Akorede, Taiwo, & Toyin, 2024) but also concerns over poor connectivity, unstable

electricity, and limited digital competence (Aliyu, 2024; Dahiru & Zaitawa, 2024). In South-West Nigeria, teachers expressed high awareness but predominantly negative attitudes, citing inadequate training and fears of job loss (Olaseni, 2024). Among pre-service teachers, moderate AI literacy and strong willingness to use AI were reported, though accompanied by significant training needs (Ayanwale et al., 2024).

Taken together, these studies highlight a paradox: while Nigerian educators generally recognize the potential of AI to support innovative pedagogies, actual implementation remains constrained by systemic barriers. The findings also suggest variation across stakeholder groups—teachers, school leaders, and pre-service educators—indicating that perceptions and readiness are shaped not only by individual skills but also by institutional support, infrastructural realities, and broader policy environments. This aligns with the Quadruple Helix framework, which emphasizes the interplay of academia (schools and teacher training institutions), industry (technology providers such as uLesson and Afrilearn), government (through infrastructure, policy, and regulation), and civil society (including parents, communities, and advocacy groups). When viewed through this lens, existing research underscores fragmented progress: high interest and awareness from academia, innovation from industry, limited yet evolving support from government, and underexplored roles for communities in sustaining adoption. A critical gap, therefore, lies in understanding how these actors can collaborate more effectively to scale AI-driven pedagogies in Nigeria.

This study also aligns with a multi-stakeholder model of AI adoption in education, emphasizing collaboration between

educational institutions, technology providers, government, and local communities. In the Nigerian context, educational institutions play a critical role in embedding teacher training and experimenting with AI-based pedagogies, ensuring that innovations are relevant and curriculum-aligned. Technology providers supply the tools for differentiated instruction, gamification, and smart tutoring, though their effectiveness depends on contextual adaptation and accessibility. Government policy is central in creating enabling conditions through infrastructure investments, regulatory frameworks, and ethical guidelines to govern AI usage in schools. Equally important, community engagement fosters local ownership, addresses equity concerns, and ensures that AI-driven solutions are not only technically feasible but also socially acceptable. By framing adoption within this collaborative ecosystem, the present study contributes not only empirical insights but also a strategic model for AI integration in Nigerian secondary schools, one that balances global standards with local educational realities. In light of these developments, it is essential to understand the present conditions, possibilities, and challenges of AI-driven innovative teaching methods in Nigerian secondary schools. This study investigates the adoption, perception, and implementation of these new technologies and teaching approaches in Nigeria, aiming to provide actionable strategies for enhancing 21st-century learning solutions in accordance with international standards.

Research Questions

This study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. What innovative pedagogical approaches are currently being implemented in Nigerian secondary schools?
2. To what extent are AI tools integrated into the teaching and learning processes in Nigerian secondary schools?
3. What are secondary school teachers' perceptions towards AI integration in classroom instruction?
4. What are the Challenges Affecting Integration of AI and Innovative Pedagogies?

Hypotheses

Based on the research questions, the following hypothesis was tested:

1. Teachers' perceptions of AI integration did not significantly influence their adoption of innovative teaching practices.

Theoretical Framework

This research is based on three interrelated viewpoints: the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Constructivist Learning Theory, and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT). Collectively, they offer a comprehensive framework for comprehending how teachers integrate AI tools, how these tools facilitate pedagogical change, and how systemic elements influence integration. Significantly, these theories are analyzed through the Quadruple Helix innovation framework (government, academia, industry, and civil society), which highlights the cooperative ecosystem necessary for integrating AI into education in sustainable and context-aware manners.

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1989) suggests that technology adoption is primarily influenced by perceived usefulness

(PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU). In Nigerian secondary schools, TAM clarifies teachers' willingness to embrace AI tools: if educators view AI as enhancing teaching effectiveness, facilitating personalized learning, and improving student performance (PU), they are more inclined to incorporate it into their lessons. Similarly, when AI applications are available and require little technical knowledge (PEOU), their adoption is promoted even more (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000). Research shows that educators' views strongly influence the use of technology in educational settings (Lee, Ramasamy, & Subbarao, 2025). In the Quadruple Helix framework, TAM emphasizes that educational institutions (schools and teacher training colleges) should enhance digital literacy, while businesses (AI developers) must create accessible, curriculum-compatible tools. This interaction ensures that educators' views are favorably influenced by encouraging settings and practical technologies.

Constructivist Learning Theory

Constructivist Learning Theory, based on Piaget (1972) and Vygotsky (1978), highlights the importance of active, learner-focused knowledge building through collaboration, exploration, and problem resolution. AI-driven teaching methods- such as adaptive learning systems, smart tutoring, and AI simulations-reflect constructivist concepts by providing tailored feedback, enhancing engagement, and encouraging interactive learning settings (Holmes et al., 2019).

In Nigeria, where memorization typically prevails, AI tools aligned with constructivism can drive a transition to student-focused, inquiry-based classrooms. In the Quadruple Helix, constructivism indicates that the

government should update curricula and evaluation methods to promote critical thinking and creativity; civil society (parents, NGOs, communities) should endorse student-centered learning environments; and academia and industry should collaboratively create tools that correspond with these educational objectives.

Unified Acceptance and Use of Technology Theory (UTAUT)

To enhance TAM, the UTAUT model (Venkatesh et al., 2003) includes additional factors influencing technology adoption: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions. These elements are especially significant in developing environments such as Nigeria, where infrastructure, peer influence, and institutional backing greatly affect adoption results (Obanō & Osagie, 2025). For instance, poor electricity provision and restricted internet connectivity hinder facilitating conditions, whereas social norms and peer support can affect teachers' readiness to experiment with AI tools. UTAUT thus expands the emphasis from personal perceptions to systemic facilitators and obstacles, which is essential in developing strategies for sustainable integration. In the Quadruple Helix, UTAUT highlights the importance of governmental funding for infrastructure, industry innovation suitable for low-resource settings, academia to facilitate professional growth, and civil society to advocate for fair access.

Incorporating the Concepts within the Quadruple Helix

When combined, TAM and UTAUT elucidate the reasons and conditions under which educators embrace AI, whereas Constructivist Learning Theory illustrates how AI can enhance teaching methods to reach 21st-

century educational goals like teamwork, innovation, and critical thinking (Voogt & Roblin, 2012). The Quadruple Helix model places these dynamics within a larger ecosystem, highlighting that successful AI integration necessitates:

- a) Academia: fostering AI comprehension among educators and incorporating constructivist teaching methods.
- b) Industry: developing AI resources that are approachable, aligned with educational standards, and tailored to specific local needs.
- c) Government: supplying infrastructure, policy structures, and ethical supervision.
- d) Civil society: promoting fairness, cultural significance, and community stewardship.

This comprehensive viewpoint acknowledges that the sustainable implementation of AI in Nigerian secondary education relies not just on personal acceptance (TAM/UTAUT) or educational alignment (constructivism) but also on widespread cooperation among the four helices.

Methodology

This research utilized a quantitative approach to investigate the incorporation of creative teaching strategies and artificial intelligence (AI) in secondary schools in Nigeria. A sampling strategy involving multiple stages was employed.

Stage 1: Choice of State. Three states-Lagos, Edo, and Kaduna-were intentionally selected to represent Nigeria's geopolitical diversity and varying degrees of digital preparedness. Lagos, the country's economic and technological center, exemplifies strong partnerships between government and

industry in adopting EdTech. Edo has initiated state-driven reforms like the EdoBEST initiative, showcasing robust partnerships between government and academia. Kaduna, situated in the North, showcases infrastructural and socio-cultural difficulties that underscore matters of equity and inclusion. Collectively, these states provide a representative perspective of Nigeria's educational landscape.

Stage 2: Selection of Schools and Participants. In each state, ten public secondary schools were chosen at random. At least ten teachers and one school leader (principal or vice principal) were intentionally selected from each school based on their involvement in digital or innovative practices. The sample included a total of 330 educators and 30 school administrators.

Data were collected through the researcher-created AI-Pedagogy Integration Inventory (APII), which featured segments on demographics, novel teaching strategies, AI tool usage, educator attitudes, and perceived obstacles. Responses were evaluated using a 4-point Likert scale. Validation by experts ensured content accuracy, and a pilot test involving 30 non-sampled teachers resulted in a Cronbach's alpha of 0.86, verifying reliability. Surveys were conducted through both online platforms and in-person interactions over a period of six weeks. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, averages, standard deviations) and inferential statistics (Pearson's correlation and linear regression) were performed with SPSS version 26. Consent was granted by the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Education at the University of Africa, Toru-Orua, Bayelsa State. Consent was obtained, privacy was guaranteed, and involvement was optional. The research design embodies the Quadruple

Helix model by involving government (policy frameworks influencing education), academia (educators and school administrators as key participants), industry (AI solutions and EdTech collaborations),

and civil society (public educational institutions reflecting diverse communities). This alignment highlights how the integration of AI in Nigerian education results from the collaboration of various stakeholders.

Results

Research Question One: What innovative pedagogical approaches are currently being implemented in Nigerian secondary schools?

Table 1: Use of Innovative Pedagogies Approaches

S/N	Statement	Never	Rarely	Often	Always	Mean (Standard Deviation)
1	I use project-based learning to enhance student understanding.	4(1.2)	21(6.4)	30(9.1)	275(83.3)	3.75(0.63)
2	I adopt flipped classroom strategies in my lessons.	12(3.6)	4(1.2)	41(12.4)	273(82.7)	3.74(0.66)
3	I integrate blended learning in instruction	11(3.3)	30(9.1)	49(14.8)	240(72.7)	3.57(0.79)
4	I integrate gamification in classroom instruction.	10(3)	56(17)	3(9)	261(79.1)	3.56(0.88)
5	I apply inquiry-based learning techniques during instruction.	11(3.3)	36(10.9)	59(17.9)	224(67.9)	3.50(0.82)
6	I use collaborative and Peer-Learning Strategies to guide teaching.	9(2.7)	56(1.7)	54(16.4)	21(63.9)	3.42(0.86)

Table 1 presents the **innovative pedagogical approaches** currently in use in the chosen Nigerian secondary schools. The items in Table 1 had average scores exceeding the criterion mean of 2.5, indicating that most participants concurred with the items. Thus,

the creative teaching methods currently adopted in Nigerian secondary schools include project-based learning, flipped classroom techniques, blended learning, gamification, inquiry-based learning, collaborative learning, and peer learning.

Research Question Two: To what extent are AI tools integrated into the teaching and learning processes in Nigerian secondary schools?

Table 2: Extent of AI Tools Integration in Teaching and Learning in Nigerian (N = 330 Teachers)

AI Integration Area	High Extent (%)	Moderate Extent (%)	Low Extent (%)	Mean (SD)
Automated Grading & Assessment Tools	21.7	46.5	31.8	2.05(0.72)
Adaptive Learning Platforms (e.g., uLesson, Afrilearn)	27.4	36.5	36.1	1.83(0.69)
AI-Supported Tutoring/Chatbots	22.5	28.3	49.2	1.75(0.52)
Learning Analytics & Feedback Systems	26.1	38.7	35.2	2.08(0.78)
AI in Administrative Support (Timetabling, Records)	36.2	45.8	18.3	2.25(0.86)
AI-Enhanced Gamification Tools (Quizizz, Kahoot, etc.)	30.5	41.7	27.8	2.12(0.81)
Overall Extent of AI Integration	27.4	39.6	33.1	2.01(0.73)

Scale: High = 3, moderate = 2, low = 1
 Overall Mean = 2.01 indicates a **moderate extent** of AI integration

The table indicates that AI integration in Nigerian secondary schools is generally moderate (Overall Mean = 2.01), with significant differences according to functional area. Approximately 27% of the participants indicated a significant level of AI

integration overall, 40% indicated moderate integration, and 33% indicated low integration. These findings suggest that, while AI exists in schools, it is not widespread or fully integrated into daily classroom activities

Research Question Three: What are the secondary school teachers' perceptions towards AI integration in classroom instruction?

Table 3: Teachers' Perception of AI Integration

S/N	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation
1	AI makes teaching more efficient and effective.	3.70	0.67
2	I feel confident using AI tools in classroom instruction.	3.92	0.39
3	AI supports personalized learning for students.	2.97	0.94
4	I believe AI may replace the role of teachers in the future.	3.67	0.69
5	Ethical concerns such as data privacy affect my use of AI tools.	3.79	0.56
6	I do not have formal training in AI pedagogy	3.46	0.85
Grand Mean		3.59	0.68

Table 3 illustrates the perceptions of secondary school teachers regarding the integration of AI into classroom teaching. Items 1–6 in Table 4 indicate that their average scores exceeded the criterion mean of 2.5, demonstrating that the participants concurred with the items. Consequently, teachers in the chosen states perceive AI integration as follows:

they are confident in utilizing AI tools for classroom teaching, ethical issues such as data privacy influence their AI tool usage, AI enhances teaching efficiency and effectiveness, there is a possibility that AI could take over teachers' roles in the future, they lack formal training in AI education methods, and AI facilitates personalized learning for students.

Research Question Four: What are the challenges affecting the integration of AI and innovative pedagogy?

Table 4: Challenges Affecting Integration of AI and Innovative Pedagogies

S/N	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation
1	My school lacks the infrastructure (computers, internet, electricity) needed for AI-based learning.	3.84	0.41
2	I have not received adequate training on how to use AI or digital teaching tools.	3.68	0.59
3	The cost of acquiring AI tools is too high for my school.	3.65	0.65
4	The school curriculum does not support the use of innovative or AI-based pedagogy.	3.73	0.62
5	I am concerned about the privacy and ethical use of student data in AI tools.	3.70	0.64
6	I do not have enough time during the school day to implement innovative teaching strategies.	3.74	0.61
7	My students do not have access to devices or internet at home for blended/AI-supported learning.	3.75	0.51
8	There is a lack of institutional support for integrating AI in teaching.	3.46	0.85
Grand Mean		3.69	0.61

Table 4 presents the obstacles impacting the integration of AI and new teaching methods. The challenges identified by teachers include insufficient infrastructure (computers, internet, electricity) for AI-based learning; students lack access to devices or the Internet at home for blended or AI-supported learning; limited time within the school day to apply innovative teaching

methods; the school curriculum does not facilitate the use of innovative or AI-based pedagogy; concerns regarding the privacy and ethical handling of student data in AI tools; insufficient training on utilizing AI or digital teaching resources; high costs associated with acquiring AI tools; and lack of institutional support for incorporating AI in education.

Hypothesis One: Teachers’ perceptions of AI integration do not significantly influence their adoption of innovative teaching practices.

Table 5a. Means, Standard Deviations, and Correlations of Key Variables (N = 330)

Variable	Mean	SD	1	2
Adoption of Innovative Practices	3.53	0.72	1	
Perception of AI integration	3.77	0.69	0.58	1

Table 5a displays the descriptive statistics and correlations between the variables in this study. The average adoption score was 3.53 (SD = 0.72) on a 4-point scale, indicating a moderate level of innovative practice adoption. The

teachers indicated a moderately elevated perception of AI integration (M = 3.77, SD = 0.69). Teachers’ views on AI integration showed a strong positive relationship with the adoption of innovative teaching methods.

Table 5b: Linear Regression Predicting Adoption of Innovative Teaching Practices

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardize	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	d Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	12.785	1.220		10.483	0.000
	Chemistry score	0.848	0.025	0.573	33.762	0.000

Model Fit: $R^2 = 0.328$, Adjusted $R^2 = 0.327$, $F(1,326) = 1139.89$, $p < 0.000$

The complete model was significant, $F(1, 326) = 1139.89$, $p < 0.000$, with $R^2 = 0.328$, suggesting that approximately 33% of the variance in adoption was accounted for by the predictor. Teachers’ views on AI integration were a predictor ($\beta = 0.573$, $p < .000$), indicating that when educators see AI tools as advantageous for their teaching results, they are more inclined to embrace innovative instructional methods. Consequently, the results indicate that educators' views strongly affect the implementation of novel teaching methods.

Discussion of Findings

The results indicate that while conventional lecture-based teaching remains prevalent in Nigerian secondary schools, there is a slow move towards student-centered learning approaches. Methods like project-based

learning (PBL), flipped classrooms, blended learning, and gamification are gaining traction, especially in urban and private educational institutions, reflecting worldwide tendencies that highlight collaboration, critical thinking, and problem-solving (Bell, 2010; Adedoyin & Soykan, 2020). Nonetheless, differences in infrastructure and digital accessibility worsen inequalities, preventing rural and under-resourced schools from fully benefiting from these advancements. This illustrates the broader digital gap identified throughout sub-Saharan Africa (Olojo & Adewale, 2022; Yusuf et al., 2021).

The integration of AI was found to be moderate overall, with 27% of educators indicating high usage, 40% moderate, and 33% low. Though educators showed enthusiasm for AI's potential

to tailor learning, enhance efficiency, and aid differentiated instruction, worries remained regarding workload, ethics, and job stability-issues reflected in global discussions (Holmes et al., 2022; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). Essentially, the absence of infrastructure, inadequate professional training, inflexible curricula, and insufficient institutional assistance were recognized as significant obstacles. These findings highlight the disparity between educational goals and the actual classroom situation in Nigeria.

The results, in theory, endorse the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), emphasizing the impact of perceived utility, ease of use, and self-efficacy on adoption. Educators who perceived AI as advantageous and controllable were notably more inclined to incorporate it into their practices, aligning with earlier studies in education and various fields (Teo, 2011; Ifinedo, 2017; Lee, Ramasamy, & Subbarao, 2025). This confirms the explanatory strength of these models in forecasting technology adoption in education.

However, the results also emphasize that adoption cannot be comprehended only at the level of individual educators. The Quadruple Helix (QH) framework influences AI integration in education through the relationships between policy, industry, academia, and civil society. Initially, government policy plays a crucial role in tackling infrastructural disparities, revising educational programs, and establishing ethical guidelines to guarantee accountable AI implementation. Additionally, collaborations between industries and EdTech companies (such as uLesson, Afrilearn) can enhance the availability of localized AI resources and provide scalable training programs for

educators. Third, educators and school administrators in academia must lead pedagogical innovation by integrating AI into constructivist, student-centered methodologies. Ultimately, civil society, encompassing parents and local communities, affects adoption by influencing demand, offering support, and tackling socio-cultural obstacles to digital learning.

Positioning the results within the QH innovation framework illustrates that successful AI integration necessitates a comprehensive, multi-actor approach: funding for infrastructure and policy changes (government), accessible and context-aware technologies (industry), enhancement of professional skills and curriculum updates (academia), and support from the community (civil society). Lacking collaboration among these parties, educators must approach AI adoption on their own, perpetuating disparities between well-resourced and underfunded institutions.

In summary, this research indicates that educators' views and mindsets are crucial for AI implementation, yet ongoing integration relies on collaborative efforts within the larger innovation ecosystem. Placing AI integration within the Quadruple Helix model offers a structure for comprehending existing issues while also serving as a guide for engaging stakeholders to promote fair, twenty-first-century education in Nigeria.

Conclusion

This study explored the incorporation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and creative teaching methods in Nigerian secondary schools as a means to attain 21st-century education. The results indicate that although AI has considerable potential to revolutionize education via personalization, efficiency, and improved engagement, various obstacles

hinder its successful implementation. These include insufficient digital infrastructure, restricted teacher capabilities, curriculum deficiencies, and socioeconomic limitations. Despite these obstacles, this research emphasizes that combining AI with new teaching methods is not only beneficial but also crucial for preparing Nigerian students with the critical thinking, problem-solving, and digital literacy abilities needed in today's knowledge-based economy. To achieve this transformation, policymakers, educators, and stakeholders must take intentional action to enhance infrastructure, revise curricula, and ensure ongoing professional development for teachers.

Inclusive policies and practices are essential to guarantee that AI-powered innovations serve all students, particularly those in rural and underserved communities. By encouraging cooperation among government bodies, educational institutions, tech firms, and local communities, Nigeria can create a supportive environment that facilitates successful AI integration in education. In summary, despite the existing challenges, the incorporation of AI and creative teaching methods offers a strategic opportunity to enhance Nigerian secondary education for global importance. When effectively utilized, it can close learning gaps, promote fairness, and equip students with meaningful engagement in the workforce and society of the 21st century.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion, the study recommends the following:

1. The Federal Ministry of Education needs to create a thorough policy framework that offers clear direction for integrating AI and modern teaching approaches in secondary education while also

implementing ethical protections, fairness initiatives, and data privacy standards. This policy must be collaboratively developed with feedback from industry professionals, scholars, and community organizations to guarantee contextual significance.

2. The Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) must update the secondary school curriculum to incorporate AI literacy, computational thinking, and problem-solving skills that match global 21st-century competencies. Partnerships with universities and research organizations can ensure that curriculum changes are rooted in evidence, while local community participants can help tailor content to regional requirements.
3. National teacher training programs need to include AI and innovative pedagogy components through cooperative platforms among universities, teacher training institutions, and EdTech firms. These collaborations can provide both theoretical foundations and practical, technology-driven training while maintaining scalability.
4. Teachers are encouraged to implement student-centered methods like project-based learning, flipped classrooms, and inquiry-focused techniques, enhanced by AI-driven tools. Community-supported professional learning groups can improve peer learning and ongoing professional development.
5. The capacity of educators to utilize AI for personalized learning relies on dependable infrastructure. Therefore, community involvement efforts (such as parent-teacher associations, local NGOs, and public-private partnerships) must be activated to support the advancement of school-level infrastructure (for instance,

internet connectivity, electricity, and devices). Investment from both government and the private sector should back these community initiatives to reduce the gaps between urban and rural schools.

References

- Adebayo, A. M., & Olanrewaju, G. B. (2022). Challenges facing the Nigerian education system and prospects for reform. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 13(4), 21–29. <https://doi.org/10.7176/JEP>
- Adedoyin, O. B., & Soykan, E. (2020). COVID-19 pandemic and online learning: The challenges and opportunities. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 3, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2020.1813180>
- Adetutu-Awoyele, A. A., Adeowu, W. A., & Oladejo, B. (2024). Enhancing classroom learning: Impact of AI-based instruction on engagement and outcomes. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)*, 8(3), 137–145. <https://doi.org/10.47772/IJRISS.2024.803429S>
- Akorede, A. A, Taiwo, O. T., & Toyin, A. O. (2024). Teachers' perception towards the integration of Artificial Intelligence in the teaching of Mathematics in senior secondary school. *Jurnal Pendidikan Matematika dan Sains*, 12(2), 154–161.
- Aliyu, F. (2024). Teachers' awareness and perception of AI tools in chemistry education at secondary schools in Sokoto State. *RIJESSU*. Retrieved from <https://rijessu.com/volume-3/>
- Ayanwale, M. A., et al. (2024). *Examining artificial intelligence literacy among pre-service teachers in Nigeria*. *Discover Education*, 3(2), 12-24.
- Bell, S. (2010). Project-based learning for the 21st century: Skills for the future. *The Clearing House*, 83(2), 39–43. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00098650903505415>
- Chukwuma, C. M., & Okeke, N. L. (2025). AI and implementation of innovative teaching methods in 21st-century secondary education in Rivers State. *Journal of Advanced Education Management and Policy Planning*, 5(1), 275–284. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15082194>
- Dahiru, A., & Zaitawa, M. A. (2024). Integration of AI in improving secondary school education in Nigeria. *Kashere Journal of Education*, 7(2). <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/kje/article/view/293241>
- Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 13(3), 319–340. <https://doi.org/10.2307/249008>
- Holmes, W., Bialik, M., & Fadel, C. (2019). *Artificial Intelligence in Education: Promises and Implications for Teaching and Learning*. Center for Curriculum Redesign.
- Ifinedo, P. (2017). Examining students' intention to continue using blogs for learning: Perspectives from technology acceptance, motivational, and social-cognitive frameworks. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 72, 189–199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2016.12.049>
- Lee, A. T., Ramasamy, R. K., & Subbarao, A. (2025). Understanding psychosocial barriers to healthcare technology adoption: A Review of TAM Technology Acceptance Model and Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology and UTAUT Frameworks. *Healthcare (Basel)*, 13(3), 250. doi: 10.3390/healthcare13030250

- Luckin, R., Holmes, W., Griffiths, M., & Forcier, L. B. (2016). *Intelligence unleashed: An Argument for AI in Education*. Pearson. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.1995.7602>
- Obanō, E. J., & Osagie, C. I. (2025). Principals' adoption of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning processes in public secondary schools in Edo State. *Kontagora International Journal of Educational Research*, 2(2). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15082194>
- Olaseni, V. M. (2024). Teachers' perception towards integration of Artificial Intelligence tutoring-based system in the school curriculum: A survey. *E-Journal of Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences (EHASS)*, 5(13), 2242-2251.
- Olojo, O. J., & Adewale, A. O. (2022). Exploring the use of flipped classroom approach in Nigerian secondary education: Lessons from digital pedagogy. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Technology*, 5(1), 25–33.
- Piaget, J. (1972). *The psychology of the child*. New York: Basic Books.
- Teo, T. (2011). Factors influencing teachers' intention to use technology: Model development and test. *Computers & Education*, 57(4), 2432–2440. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2011.06.008>
- UNESCO. (2021). *Global Education Monitoring Report: Non-state Actors in Education—Who Chooses? Who Loses?* Retrieved from <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379875>
- Venkatesh, V., & Davis, F. D. (2000). A theoretical extension of the technology acceptance model: Four longitudinal field studies. *Management Science*, 46(2), 186–204.
- Venkatesh, V., Morris, M. G., Davis, G. B., & Davis, F. D. (2003). User acceptance of information technology: Toward a unified view. *MIS Quarterly*, 27(3), 425–478. <https://doi.org/10.2307/30036540>
- Voogt, J., & Roblin, N. P. (2012). A comparative analysis of international frameworks for 21st-century competences: Implications for national curriculum policies. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 44(3), 299–321.
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes*. Harvard University Press.
- World Bank. (2023). *Addressing the Learning Crisis with Generative AI: Lessons from Edo State, Nigeria*. <https://blogs.worldbank.org/en/developmenttalk/addressing-the-learning-crisis-with-generative-ai--lessons-from->
- Yusuf, M. O., Fakomogbon, M. A., & Omiola, M. A. (2021). Effects of gamification on students' achievement in Nigerian secondary school mathematics. *Journal of Educational Multimedia and Hypermedia*, 30(4), 401–416. <https://www.learntechlib.org/primary/p/220057/>
- Zawacki-Richter, O., Marín, V. I., Bond, M., & Gouverneur, F. (2019). Systematic review of research on artificial intelligence applications in higher education – where are the educators? *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 16(1), 39. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-019-0171-0>.